

USE OF EDUCATIONAL FLASHMOBS IN PREPARING FUTURE ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHERS FOR PROFESSIONAL AND PEDAGOGICAL ACTIVITY

Sanoeva Gulbar

Jizzakh Polytechnic Institute

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Abstract: The article highlights the possibilities of using educational flash mobs in the preparation of future English language teachers for professional-pedagogical activities.

Basic concepts: flashmob, development, language acquisition, English language, teacher's professional activity.

The studies conducted on a global scale show that today it is necessary to learn the foreign language being studied in harmony with the culture of the country where the language is being studied, to introduce the cultural studies and competence approach to the educational process, to teach the integrity and continuity of foreign language learning. providing is important in enriching the content of education.

Nowadays the world market situation has changed dramatically, and competition is becoming more and more intense in the context of globalization, so effective cooperation with the mass media in our country in the field of information policy, distribution of fast information within the framework of journalists and bloggers who work constantly with information services, as well as regulatory ensuring the participation of the broad population in the discussion of draft legal documents. Also, conducting monitoring and analysis of the information space, quickly responding to critical and widely discussed information attacks, organizing work on the dissemination of information related to the activities of relevant state bodies and organizations in the mass media and the Internet; together with state bodies and organizations, great attention is paid to the preparation of news, information, commentary and other information-analytical materials for distribution through local and foreign mass media.

Teaching English using flashboards in the context of digital technologies in higher education is considered one of the most relevant, scientific interest, multi-disciplinary fields in which many scientific researches are conducted both in foreign countries and in our country.

In order to solve the problems faced by the educational system in the innovative processes taking place at the present time, we need people who are able to absorb new information and evaluate the acquired knowledge by themselves, who make the necessary decisions, who are independent and think freely. Therefore, one of the main features of the pedagogical process in today's higher education system is determined by its digitization. Adopted on July 15, 2018 "On additional measures to encourage the implementation of innovative projects and technologies in production", published on May 28, 2012 "Training of qualified pedagogues and secondary -measures related to the further improvement of the system of providing special vocational education institutions with such personnel

on"[8, 7b.] decisions ¹emphasize the need for the potential of pedagogic personnel and their readiness to implement innovative changes in the educational system. Also adopted by the Cabinet of Ministers "On measures to create conditions for further development of computerization and information and communication technologies in places" (02.01.2012), "Measures on further development of computerization and introduction of information and communication technologies" "On Activities" (20.01.2012) and the set of activities and activities planned in the educational system for the implementation of these documents indicate that digital technologies are widely entering the life of our country.

May 27, 2013 No. 143 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan "In 2013-2016, measures to accelerate the equipping (additional equipment) of foreign language offices of educational institutions with modern information and communication, technical means and equipment for teaching about" The decision was announced. In the ²decision, in the educational process, the use of advanced pedagogical methods and technologies, information and communication technologies, electronic educational resources and multimedia presentations should be thoroughly and comprehensively studied, education taking into account foreign experience to re-develop new curricula and programs in order to organize the process in a new way, to abandon the traditional institutional education methods and to ensure the increase of hours of practical training and production practice. year, and on this basis, significant tasks in teaching English in HEIs were performed.

The implementation of innovative ideas in the educational system, the development and implementation of systems, mechanisms and technologies is becoming one of the most urgent tasks.

In the era of globalization, as a result of the integration of cultural, educational and socio-economic relations between countries, the training of specialists who can freely communicate in foreign languages, in particular, English, and at the same time be aware of the information transmitted on a global scale, are all defined in the process of educational reforms. plays an important role in the implementation of priority tasks.

In the process of higher education, with the help of digital technologies, the ground is created for students to widely use the achievements of world civilization and world information resources, the conditions and opportunities for the development of international cooperation and communication are expanded.

Nowadays in the higher education institutions of our country, great attention is paid to learning foreign languages, including English, and educational programs and plans are formed based on the trends of the times. However, there are still some controversial aspects of teaching English to students:

Firstly, the emergence of the need to update the approaches to teaching English in the currently operating HEIs;

Secondly, the increase of the student's need to improve his knowledge of the English language;

Thirdly, the outdated material and technical base in unsatisfactory pedagogical conditions, the lack of competent specialists;

Fourth, the need to improve the practice of teaching English;

¹ Collection of legal documents of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 2012, No. 22, Article 241; 2013, No. 23, Article 300

² Collection of legal documents of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 2013, No. 22, Article 283, No. 34, Article 453

for a competent specialist who speaks at least one foreign language (especially English), the increase in demand for the social order of society for the situation of practical use in his professional activity.

Due to the development of modern information and communication technologies and tools in the education system of developed countries such as the USA, Great Britain, Germany, China, the need for forms of language acquisition through the use of electronic services by education consumers is increasing, and this Extensive research is being conducted in the field.

During our research, we began to develop professional competencies in future teachers based on teaching flashbacks. For this, we are in the first stages of research (2019-2021). We have developed proposals for the use of Flashbom technologies in the educational process.

Educational flasmobs are pre-planned learning activities in which a large group of students perform pre-planned learning activities. A flash mob is a type of smart mob. Gathering of flashmob participants is carried out using electronic means of communication. So what exactly is a mob? How can it be used in education?

Martmob is a "smart mob" activity related to digital technologies, aimed at developing communication skills. This concept was introduced by Howard Reinhold in his 2002 book Smart Gangs: The Next Social Revolution. Reinhold defined a smart crowd as follows: "A smart crowd is made up of people who can act in concert even if they don't know each other...because they have the ability to communicate and compute.

"These technologies that support smart swarms include the Internet, computer communications such as Internet Relay Chat, and wireless devices such as cell phones and personal digital assistants. Methodologies such as peer-to-peer networks and ubiquitous computing are also changing the way people organize and share information" [p. 5,67]. Smart mobs are sometimes manipulated by dispatchers who operate a "mobbing system" (i.e., those who have a contact list and the means to send instant messages to the group) to keep the dynamics of smart mobbing "hidden" and not discuss such incidents on the Internet. there is a trend.

Flashmob technology on a global scale , the need for students to develop English speaking techniques, and the need for quick training based on the mnemonic base, shows the need to improve their professional-pedagogical diagnostics. Within the framework of the research, we used F leshmob technology to organize experiential training for the development of professional competence of future foreign (English) language teachers .

F leshmob technology

Flashmob technology is effective in helping students learn foreign languages and includes dozens of questions and hundreds of associated words. Mobile high-speed packets like HSDPA and web cameras come in handy when using flash mobs.

As a result of these words and phrases, the opportunity for the student to remember the words and phrases formed within the studied topic on the basis of answering logically coherent questions increases. This technology is based on the creation of connections and ideas that are not on the surface, but have opportunities for development and improvement, within the framework of the problem being studied. Also, Flash mob technology can be used to solve everyday problems, life situations, etc.

Some people are ready to come up with all sorts of new ideas easily, while others can't come up with anything interesting beyond just one or two ideas, even after a quick brainstorm. This

shows that different people have different thinking and abilities [p. 2,34 .]. A similar process of reflection occurs in the educational process. Flash mob technology helps students come up with new ideas . Flash mob technology is a system of asking specific questions that encourages the generation of new ideas.

In other words, Flash mob technology is considered a creative technique .

During our research **We were able to** approve flash mob technology with 1 course in the 1st semester. For this, students were presented with a text on the topic "Abul Kasim az-Zamakhshari" in the 1st semester.

Abul Kasim al-Zamakhshari

(Excerpt from the text)

Many great scientists who made a worthy contribution to the development of world science and culture grew up in the land of ancient Khorezm. Abul Kasim az-Zamakhshari is one of these great figures. Allama's full name is Abul Qasim ibn Umar al-Zamakhshari , and he was born on the 27th day of the month of Rajab ^{467Ah} in the village of Zamakhshar, one of the Qasabas of Khorezm. Information about az-Zamakhshari is mainly given in medieval Arabic sources.

Although his father was not very wealthy, he was a literate, person who spent most of his time reciting the Qur'an and praying, and also served as an imam in a mosque in Zamakhshar. Az-Zamakhshari's mother was also considered one of the religious women. It seems that al-Zamakhshari's father was a nobleman. For example , the poet writes in one of his odes that his father worked tirelessly to earn a living because he had many children and a large family.

Az-Zamakhshari family belongs to Mu'tazili teachings of Islam , young Mahmud's worldview was formed under the influence of this religious, pious Father, and he also received the first knowledge from his own father. Its known from the information about alloma that one of his legs was made of wood, and because he wore his long jacket down, the tall man thought he was lame. (Appendix 3)

above text based on Flash mob technology, the students were asked to replace the information in the table below with the relevant information in the context of the text. For this, the students of the 1st stage began to fill in the following table(-table).

	Text replaced by students
Submitted text	
Allama's full name is Abul Qasim ibn Umar Al-Zamakhshari , and he was born on the 27th day of the month of Rajab ^{467Ah} in the village of Zamakhshar, one of the Qasabas of Khorezm.	Our compatriot Az Zamakhshari, who founded the Arabic alphabet, was born in Khorezm on the 27th of the month of Rajab in 4 67

	Combination (combined) text by students
Text provided by flashmob	
Although his father was not very wealthy, he	The fact that his father and mother were religious, spent their time reciting the

<p>was a literate, person who spent most of his time reciting the Qur'an and praying, and also served as an imam in a mosque in Zamakhshar. Az-Zamakhshari's mother was also considered one of the religious women.</p>	<p>Qur'an and praying played an important role in their child's upbringing. Farzandi-Az Zamakhshari grew up honest, conscientious, and thirsty for knowledge.</p>

This based on the examples given above, the students were able to work with the text and demonstrate their scientific competence in English. For them, this technology served as a very interesting and motivating technology. Also, on the basis of this technology, students learned to understand English words, phrases, sentences in the text, to find and replace them, to adapt the text to the situation, to react to it. Before using this technology, it was necessary to clearly define the task, that is, the problem to be solved or the idea to be developed was determined. In addition, it was found during research that this technology can be used in a completely new field. Students learned that it can be used in personal life, family relationships, work, business, provision of goods and services, and other situations.

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